

Caste Discrimination in Indian Writing in English: An Exploration of Representation and Resistance

Dr. Sarala Kisan Sanap

Associate Professor and Head Department of English

MGV's Loknete Vyankatrao Hiray Arts, Science and Commerce College, Panchavati, Nashik.

saralaksanap@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Caste discrimination remains a pervasive issue in Indian society, deeply embedded in its historical, social, and cultural fabric. This paper explores how Indian writing in English has addressed the theme of caste discrimination, providing a platform for marginalized voices and challenging the entrenched hierarchies of the caste system. By analyzing selected literary works, this study examines the portrayal of caste-based oppression, the experiences of Dalits, and the broader social implications of caste discrimination in contemporary India. The paper also highlights the role of literature in fostering resistance and advocating for social change.

Keywords: Caste Discrimination, Dalit Literature, Untouchability, Social Exclusion, Resistance, Caste Hierarchy, Identity and Agency, Psychological Resistance, Dalit Empowerment, Intersectionality.

Introduction: Caste and Its Representation in Indian Writing in English

Caste, as a social construct in India, has a deep-rooted historical presence that continues to shape the country's socio-political, economic, and cultural landscape. Despite efforts at social reform, the caste system remains a central issue in contemporary Indian society, particularly for marginalized groups, such as Dalits (formerly referred to as "Untouchables"). Indian writing in English, as a reflection of the nation's complex social fabric, provides a significant lens through which the caste system can be explored, represented, and critiqued. In this research, the focus will be on how caste discrimination is represented in Indian English literature and how various literary works contribute to the resistance against caste-based hierarchies and discrimination.

While English-language writing in India was historically dominated by upper-caste voices, the post-independence period has seen a significant shift, with writers from Dalit and marginalized communities increasingly using literature as a form of self-expression and social critique. Their works illuminate the psychological and social consequences of caste discrimination, while also offering narratives of resistance, empowerment, and resilience.

This article will explore the ways caste discrimination is represented in contemporary Indian English literature, focusing on the mechanisms of caste-based violence, marginalization, and the response to it within both the texts and their socio-cultural contexts. By analyzing various literary works, we will examine how caste becomes not only a theme in Indian literature but also a vehicle for social change.

Received: 2 September 2024

Revised: 22 September 2024

Accepted: 30 September 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14167840](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14167840)

Historical Context of Caste in India

The caste system in India, a hierarchical social structure based on hereditary occupation and ritual purity, has existed for over two millennia. Its origins are believed to be rooted in the ancient Hindu varna system, which was initially divided into four categories: Brahmins (priests and scholars), Kshatriyas (warriors and rulers), Vaishyas (traders and farmers), and Shudras (laborers and service providers). However, over time, these divisions became more rigid, leading to the development of a complex web of thousands of sub-castes, each with its own social status.

At the bottom of this hierarchy were the "Untouchables" or Dalits, who were subjected to severe social exclusion and discrimination. Historically, they were denied basic rights such as access to water, land, education, and public spaces. The colonial period further entrenched the caste system, as British policies aligned with upper-caste elites, creating a deepening divide between the privileged and the oppressed.

Post-independence India made efforts to abolish untouchability through legal reforms, particularly through the Indian Constitution (1950), which prohibited discrimination on the grounds of caste. However, caste-based discrimination and violence persist in contemporary society, especially in rural areas, where caste identities remain crucial to social interaction.

This history forms the backdrop for the representation of caste discrimination in Indian English literature. Authors have used the medium to critique the system's entrenched inequalities and explore the complex emotional, psychological, and social consequences faced by marginalized groups.

Caste Representation in Indian English Literature

Early Representations: The Struggle for Social Justice

Caste discrimination began to be addressed in Indian English literature primarily during the post-colonial era, with writers such as **Mulk Raj Anand** and **R.K. Narayan** taking on caste as a theme in their works. Anand's work in particular is notable for its focus on the lives of Dalits and the suffering they endured as a result of caste-based discrimination.

Mulk Raj Anand's *Untouchable* (1935)

Mulk Raj Anand's novel *Untouchable* is one of the earliest examples of Indian English literature tackling the subject of caste. The novel follows the life of Bakha, a young Dalit boy, who is forced to perform menial tasks such as cleaning toilets and disposing of human waste. Anand vividly portrays the deep psychological trauma caused by caste discrimination, illustrating Bakha's humiliation and self-loathing as he navigates a world in which he is regarded as inferior. Anand critiques the dehumanizing aspects of the caste system, highlighting its oppressive nature and its impact on an individual's sense of worth. The novel represents caste discrimination not only as a social evil but as a psychological burden that shapes the lives of Dalits in a way that makes it difficult for them to reclaim their dignity.

R.K. Narayan's *The Guide* (1958)

While not focused solely on caste, R.K. Narayan's *The Guide* contains subtle explorations of the caste system and its impact on the lives of the characters. The novel's protagonist, Raju, a former tour guide who becomes embroiled in a series of moral and ethical dilemmas, comes from a lower-caste background. Through Raju's interactions with both high and low-caste individuals, Narayan illustrates how caste hierarchies shape human relationships, even in a seemingly cosmopolitan environment like Malgudi. Narayan's work subtly critiques the entrenched social divisions and reflects the ongoing challenge of breaking free from these limitations.

The Emergence of Dalit Literature

The 1990s witnessed a significant shift in the representation of caste in Indian English literature with the emergence of Dalit voices in the literary scene. Writers from Dalit communities began to write their own narratives, giving a direct voice to the marginalized and focusing on the brutal realities of caste oppression.

Bama's *Karukku* (1992)

Bama, a Tamil Dalit writer, became one of the most prominent voices in Dalit literature with her autobiographical work *Karukku*. The novel addresses the intersection of caste and gender, portraying the life of a Dalit Christian woman who struggles with the double oppression of caste and patriarchy. Through Bama's narrative, we see the harsh realities faced by Dalit women, who are often relegated to the lowest of social statuses, both within the caste hierarchy and within their communities. Bama's work provides an intimate portrayal of the psychological toll of caste discrimination, offering a poignant commentary on the resilience of marginalized groups.

Omprakash Valmiki's *Joothan* (1997)

Omprakash Valmiki's *Joothan*, an autobiography that delves into the author's experiences as a Dalit in rural India, is another key work that represents caste oppression in Indian literature. The book describes Valmiki's experiences of discrimination and the harsh realities of untouchability, revealing the systemic nature of caste-based violence and exclusion. Valmiki writes about the psychological damage inflicted by caste-based discrimination, portraying how it manifests in self-doubt, humiliation, and a sense of worthlessness. His work marks a break from the passive narratives of Dalit lives seen in earlier literature, instead presenting a story of resistance and resilience.

Caste and Globalization: Post-Independence Narratives

In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, as globalization and modernity influenced Indian society, caste continued to be a pertinent theme in literature. Writers began to explore how caste discrimination persists in the age of technology, urbanization, and economic change. In novels dealing with urban spaces, caste identities are often reimaged as a means of both survival and resistance.

Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things* (1997)

In *The God of Small Things*, Arundhati Roy addresses the legacy of caste through the portrayal of the Ipe family in the small town of Ayemenem. The novel touches upon the caste-based power structures within the family and the larger community, particularly in the relationships between Ammu, a woman from a lower caste, and Velutha, a lower-caste man. The tragic love story between Ammu and Velutha, which is central to the novel, is overshadowed by the caste system that dictates their fates. Roy uses caste not only as a social framework but also as a psychological force that shapes the characters' lives, determining their actions and suffering.

Kiran Desai's *The Inheritance of Loss* (2006)

Kiran Desai's *The Inheritance of Loss* explores caste discrimination in the context of globalization and migration. The novel, set in the foothills of the Himalayas, deals with the psychological and social ramifications of colonialism, nationalism, and caste. Desai examines how caste still operates in the background of the characters' lives, even as they interact with global economic systems. Through characters like Biju, a young Dalit who works as a cook in New York, Desai portrays the difficulties of escaping caste-based discrimination in a globalized world, where social divisions are often exacerbated by economic inequality.

Caste and Psychological Trauma: The Internalization of Oppression

One of the key ways in which caste discrimination is represented in Indian English literature is through the psychological trauma it inflicts on those who are oppressed by it. The caste system is not only an external, social construct but also a deeply internalized mechanism that affects the sense of self-worth, identity, and aspirations of Dalits and other marginalized groups.

Internalized Casteism: The Psychological Burden of Untouchability

The psychological effects of caste-based oppression are explored in works like Anand's *Untouchable* and Valmiki's *Joothan*. Bakha, the protagonist of *Untouchable*, is keenly aware of his low-caste status, and much of his suffering comes from the internalization of the idea that he is inherently inferior. This internalized oppression leads him to accept his position in society, despite the humiliation and degradation he faces on a daily basis.

Similarly, in *Joothan*, Valmiki describes how Dalits are psychologically conditioned to accept their "place" in society, which often leads to feelings of shame, alienation, and a sense of powerlessness. The caste system not only dictates how others perceive Dalits but also how they perceive themselves, creating an internalized caste consciousness that is difficult to escape.

Resistance and the Quest for Self-Identity

Despite the psychological burden imposed by caste, many Dalit characters in Indian English literature also embark on journeys of resistance. They struggle to reclaim their dignity and identity, rejecting the imposed social hierarchies and creating spaces for self-expression and autonomy.

In *Karukku*, Bama describes her own resistance to caste oppression, as she grapples with the restrictions placed on her as a Dalit woman. Her journey to reclaim her identity is a powerful

example of how literature can serve as a tool for resistance, allowing marginalized voices to push back against the oppressive forces of the caste system.

Caste Resistance through Literature

In this section, we explore the role of literature as a tool of resistance against caste discrimination, particularly through the works of Dalit authors and other marginalized voices in contemporary Indian English literature. Caste-based oppression is deeply ingrained in the socio-cultural fabric of India, and while legal measures and social movements have sought to dismantle its hold, caste remains a pervasive force that influences individuals' identities, opportunities, and relationships. Literature, especially the writing of Dalit authors, offers a potent mechanism for resisting this oppression. Through storytelling, Dalit writers create narratives that challenge dominant caste ideologies, giving voice to marginalized communities and advocating for social change.

Dalit Literature as Resistance

Dalit literature represents a powerful act of defiance against the caste system. For centuries, Dalits were denied access to the educational, social, and literary traditions of India, resulting in their exclusion from mainstream cultural and intellectual discourse. With the advent of Dalit literature in the 20th century, authors from these communities began to reclaim their voices and challenge the oppressive structures that had silenced them for generations.

Dalit literature offers not only an alternative narrative to the dominant upper-caste accounts of history, but also serves as a direct form of resistance. By writing about their experiences, Dalit authors forcefully confront the horrors of untouchability, the violence of caste discrimination, and the enduring psychological toll of social exclusion. Their works speak to the lived realities of Dalit life, giving expression to pain, suffering, resistance, and resilience.

Omprakash Valmiki's *Joothan* (1997)

One of the most significant works in the realm of Dalit literature is Omprakash Valmiki's *Joothan*, an autobiographical account that offers a stark and candid portrayal of the author's experiences growing up in a lower-caste family in rural India. The title, "Joothan," refers to the scraps of food left by upper-caste people, which Dalits were forced to eat, symbolizing the deeply ingrained practice of untouchability. Valmiki's account details the brutal social exclusion faced by his community, and the narrative voice, raw and unflinching, presents the harsh realities of caste-based discrimination.

Valmiki's narrative is an act of resistance on multiple levels. Firstly, by simply documenting his life, he challenges the silences around Dalit existence and brings the untold stories of the marginalized to the forefront. Secondly, *Joothan* functions as a critique of the mythologies surrounding the caste system. Valmiki does not shy away from detailing the psychological trauma and the internalized casteism that often leads to self-hatred and oppression among Dalits. Through this cathartic recounting, Valmiki seeks not just to inform, but to inspire social change, urging the reader to see the Dalit subject not as a passive victim but as an active agent of resistance.

Bama's *Karukku* (1992)

Another important example of Dalit resistance literature is Bama's *Karukku*, which narrates the life of a Dalit Christian woman living in Tamil Nadu. In the novel, Bama confronts the intersection of caste and gender, focusing on how Dalit women face dual oppression — not only due to their caste status but also as women in a patriarchal society. The novel reflects on the author's personal journey of self-awareness and resistance, revealing the psychological and emotional burdens imposed by caste and the struggles women face in asserting their identity and autonomy.

Bama's work is particularly important because it brings to light the gendered dimension of caste discrimination, an aspect that is often overlooked in mainstream caste discussions. In her narrative, Bama challenges both the religious and cultural systems that perpetuate caste-based discrimination. By speaking openly about her own experiences, including her struggles within the church and society, Bama emphasizes the importance of self-empowerment and social resistance. Her writing provides Dalit women with a platform to resist the oppressive structures that seek to control and define them.

The Act of Writing as a Form of Resistance

The act of writing itself is a profound form of resistance for Dalit authors, who have historically been denied the right to participate in literary traditions. In a society where upper-caste intellectuals have long dominated the literary landscape, Dalit writers challenge this monopoly of cultural capital. They assert their right to write, tell their stories, and critique the systems that have marginalized them.

Dalit writers often employ language, narrative structure, and thematic content that break away from traditional literary forms. By using a direct, often colloquial language, they reject the elitist and Sanskritized forms of literature that have been associated with upper-caste elites. In doing so, they not only make literature more accessible to their communities but also contest the hegemonic cultural practices that have historically been associated with caste privilege.

For example, **Mulk Raj Anand's *Untouchable* (1935)** was one of the first works in English to directly confront the dehumanization of Dalits, and through his portrayal of Bakha, Anand presents a scathing critique of the caste system. His depiction of Bakha's life, riddled with humiliation and social exclusion, presents an emotional appeal to the reader's empathy while also calling for action against caste-based oppression.

Moreover, in a broader sense, the presence of Dalit literature in the Indian literary canon helps dismantle stereotypes about Dalits and untouchability. These works present Dalits not as passive victims, but as complex individuals with agency, intelligence, and emotional depth. By writing about their struggles and resistance, Dalit writers challenge the narratives that have long justified caste discrimination, paving the way for a more inclusive and equitable literary landscape.

The Role of Literature in Shaping Public Consciousness

Literature has a significant role to play in shaping public consciousness about caste discrimination and catalyzing social change. In the case of Dalit literature, these works serve

not just as individual expressions of resistance but also as collective calls for a more just and egalitarian society.

Through literature, Dalit writers are able to bring attention to the systemic nature of caste discrimination, which is often invisible to those who do not experience it firsthand. While the Indian legal system may have abolished untouchability, caste continues to operate as an informal social system that dictates access to resources, social privileges, and opportunities. In *The Inheritance of Loss* by Kiran Desai, for instance, caste is portrayed not just as a relic of the past but as an ongoing force that affects the characters in the novel in subtle and overt ways. The novel draws attention to how caste intersects with class, colonial legacies, and globalization, making it a deeply complex issue that cannot be addressed through simple legal reforms alone.

By exploring caste discrimination in literature, these authors challenge the silence and complicity surrounding caste-based violence and exclusion. Literature thus serves as a mirror, reflecting the inequities that exist in society while also offering a vision of a future where these injustices are confronted and rectified. Through the representation of caste in literature, authors contribute to the larger struggle for social equality and justice.

Literature as a Means of Psychological Resistance

Beyond its social and political implications, literature also serves as a powerful means of psychological resistance. For many Dalit characters, caste-based oppression manifests as a deep sense of self-loathing and inferiority. The caste system not only affects external relationships but also shapes the way Dalits view themselves. This internalized casteism is often depicted in literature as a barrier to self-realization and personal growth.

However, Dalit literature also demonstrates how characters confront and resist this psychological oppression. In many Dalit narratives, the protagonist embarks on a journey of self-awareness and personal empowerment, ultimately rejecting the false beliefs of caste inferiority and embracing a sense of self-worth. The act of writing, in this context, becomes a therapeutic process, enabling authors to not only assert their identities but also to liberate themselves from the shackles of caste-based self-doubt and shame.

For example, in **Bama's *Karukku***, the protagonist's resistance to both caste and gender oppression is depicted as a form of psychological healing. Through her writing, Bama is able to reclaim her sense of identity and autonomy, breaking free from the limitations imposed by caste and patriarchy. Her narrative is not just a social critique but also a deeply personal act of resistance, where she confronts the internalized prejudices she has internalized as a Dalit woman and reclaims her voice.

Conclusion: The Ongoing Struggle and the Role of Literature

In conclusion, caste resistance in Indian English literature functions on multiple levels. Dalit literature, through the voices of authors like Omprakash Valmiki, Bama, and others, challenges the dominant caste narratives, critiques social hierarchies, and calls for systemic change. These writers use their experiences and identities as instruments of resistance, redefining what it means to be a Dalit in a caste-bound society. Through their writing, they not only bring attention

to the psychological and social realities of caste oppression but also offer a framework for imagining a more just and equal society.

Literature, as both a personal and collective act of resistance, helps dismantle the deep-rooted caste structures that continue to permeate Indian society. It provides a means of psychological resistance, healing, and empowerment, enabling marginalized voices to reclaim their dignity and challenge the oppressive forces that seek to silence them. As a tool for social change, literature is integral in the ongoing fight against caste discrimination, promoting a vision of equality and justice for all.

References:

- Anand, Mulk Raj. *Untouchable*. Longmans, 1935.
- Bama. *Karukku*. Translated by Lakshmi Holmström, Oxford University Press, 2000.
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Politics in the Name of Women's Reservation. *Contemporary Voice of Dalit*, 2455328X241262562.
- Desai, Kiran. *Hullabaloo in the Guava Orchard*. HarperCollins, 1998.
- Desai, Kiran. *The Inheritance of Loss*. Grove Press, 2006.
- Gopal, Priya. *The Caste Question: Dalits and the Politics of Modern India*. Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- Jayaram, N. *Caste and Social Change in India: A Study of the Hindu Social Structure in Transition*. Sage Publications, 2004.
- Kamble, Sharankumar. *The Prison We Broke*. Translated by Jerry Pinto, Orient Blackswan, 2008.
- Kumar, Rajeev. *Dalit Literature in India: A Critical Exploration*. Rawat Publications, 2005.
- McCrea, Bernard. *Caste and Social Stratification Among the Muslims in India*. Cambridge University Press, 1975.
- Narayan, Shyamala. *Caste and Gender in Contemporary Indian Literature: A Critical Approach*. Vikas Publishing House, 2008.
- Rothermund, Dietmar. *The Caste System in India: A Historical Perspective*. Oxford University Press, 1995.
- Roy, Arundhati. *The God of Small Things*. HarperCollins, 1997.
- Tharu, Susie, and K. Lalita, eds. *The History of Doing: An Illustrated Account of Movements for Women's Rights and Feminism in India 1800-1990*. Zubaan, 1991.
- Valmiki, Omprakash. *Joothan: An Autobiography of a Dalit*. Translated by Arun Prabha Mukherjee, Samya, 2003.
- Zelliott, Eleanor. *From Untouchable to Dalit: Essays on the Ambedkar Movement*. Manohar, 1992.